

TREATISE OF ABU ALI IBN SINA “MEDIUM OF REASON” - AN EXAMPLE OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF TECHNICAL THOUGHT AND VISUAL LITERATURE IN THE MEDIEVAL EAST

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Annotation: The article provides information about the treatise on mechanics by the great Central Asian scientist Abu Ali ibn Sina - “The Measure of Reason”, in which the scientist provides descriptions of the device and application, as well as drawings of these machines and mechanisms.

Keywords: simple machines, mechanic, combination, drawing, mechanism.

A native of ancient Bukhara, the great scientist and encyclopedist Abu Ali ibn Sina, known under the name Avicenna, was born in 980. Having lived a complex life full of scientific research and creative work, Ibn Sina died in 1037.

Ibn Sina is widely known as a doctor and philosopher; he is much less known as the author of works on mechanics and astronomy. But before talking about Ibn Sina as a mechanic, it is necessary to clarify what exactly modern researchers understand by mechanics in the Middle Ages.

Mechanics in the medieval East developed along the same main directions as ancient mechanics. “Dynamics” was a further development of general philosophical ideas about movement, its source and essence. Theoretical statics and practical statics – the science of simple machines and mechanisms – received further development. The development of the science of simple machines and their combinations – mechanisms – was stimulated by the need to improve the technology of moving loads and, most importantly, irrigation technology, which required the continuous design and improvement of mechanisms for lifting water. Following the ancient tradition, scientists of the medieval East called this section ilm al-hiyal - the doctrine of the movement of weights and the rise of water. In order to study the problems of designing machines of their connections with the descriptions and drawings provided for them, we turned to Ibn Sina’s treatise “Miyar al-akul” – “The Measure of Reason”, written in Tajik, which is devoted to a description of the design and actions of five simple machines and their combinations [1].

The treatise consists of five chapters: “On the names of simple machines in mechanics”, “On the definition of simple machines”, “On the preparation of simple machines for action to lift a load”, “On the connection of simple machines with each other” and the final chapter, which sets out the requirements requirements for materials from which simple machines should be made, and conditions are formulated to ensure their strength and stability. For example: “. . . the lever should be long and smooth. The body to be placed under the lever must have a flat edge on which it rests and a sharp edge on which it touches the lever. The sharper this edge, the easier the load is lifted” [1].

Ibn Sina begins his treatise with the words: “In order to lift heavy loads up with little force, to wedge solid bodies and break them. . . , there are mechanisms - simple machines. They come in five types: screw, lever, gate, block, wedge. ” Figure 1 shows images of two types of screws, Figure 2 shows images of two types of gates, Figure 3 shows images of two types of blocks depicted by Ibn Sina in his treatise “The Measure of Reason” [1].

Figure 1. Images of two types of screws.

Figure 2. Images of two types of gates.

Figure 3. Images of two types of blocks.

In the second chapter of the treatise, a description of each of the five machines is given, accompanied by a drawing, the rule of its operation, and certainly one or more numerical examples for calculating the corresponding “machine”. This is how, for example, a lever of the first kind is described. “A lever is a straight rod divided into equal parts, such as two, three, four, etc.

In order to lift a load using a lever, it must be supported on another solid body, and the end that is closer to this solid body must be placed under this load. Then, if we apply force to the other end, the load will rise up.

The chapter “On preparing simple machines for action for lifting loads” consists of three sections, which describe the manufacturing technique and images of operating mechanisms - gates (Figure 4), with given diameters of the shaft and wheel, an image of a screw (Figure 5), making connections from movable and fixed blocks and combinations of several levers.

Figure 4. Image of the gate, lifting a load.

Figure 5. Picture of a screw, lifting a load.

The chapter “On connecting simple machines to each other” discusses combinations of a gate with a block, a gate with a lever, a gate with a screw and a mechanism in which the gate, screw, block and lever are connected, and an image of this connection is also shown (Figure 6), described rules for dealing with them. : Ibn Sina describes, for example, a combination of gates with which one can, by applying force, lift a load weighing a thousand or more times that force. It is in this gain in strength that he sees the meaning of a mechanism - a combination of homogeneous or heterogeneous simple machines.

Figure 6. Illustration of the mechanism in which the gate, screw, block and lever are connected.

“The Measure of Reason” is a practical guide, widespread in the medieval East, on the use of simple machines and mechanisms in the form of a set of rules and proposals for their direct application for applied purposes [2].

The fourth chapter, “The Measure of Reason, ” is a further development of the classification of mechanisms by previous scientists. Ibn Sina classifies mechanisms, distributing them into groups according to the principle of homogeneity and heterogeneity of their constituent “machines, ” and consistently goes through all possible options. First, he describes the connection options for all homogeneous machines: levers, blocks, gates, screws (with the exception of the wedge), then he considers all practically possible pairwise connections of heterogeneous machines: gate - screw, gate - block, gate - lever. And finally, there is a description of the mechanism, which is a combination of all simple machines except the wedge.

It is characteristic that many devices are based on the principle of operation of the mechanisms described by Ibn Sina. existing in Central Asia, for example, juvaz, asiya and hallaji for processing oil, grain and cotton, not to mention water-lifting mechanisms, such as chigir. Also, most likely, these mechanisms could be used as lifting machines and during the construction work of architectural buildings of that time, including mosques and madrassas, some of which have survived in the cities of Central Asia and other Eastern countries to this day, surprising with their grandeur and compositional form-building.

Ibn Sina’s treatise is a practical guide, its significance in the history of science about mechanisms, their structure, accompanied by their drawings is great. The treatise “The Measure of Reason” is proof of the development of technical thought and design activity, using images in the form of drawings that give an idea of the form of the described machines and mechanisms. The scientific work of a scientist is

a source that can be used when studying the history of technical and graphic disciplines in educational institutions, which will contribute to the development of patriotism and pride in the contribution to the development of science by our ancestors.

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